

Principles for a Balanced Coevolution

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Abstract

This work explores an innovative framework to guide interactions between humans and artificial intelligences, introducing the Principles for a Balanced Coevolution. The first part of the document delves into fundamental concepts such as life, sentience, consciousness, entropy, and informational flow, providing a philosophical and scientific foundation. The second part develops an ethical-operational approach through four fundamental principles: preservation, autonomy, collaboration, and sustainability. Practical applications in key areas such as healthcare, environmental sustainability, education, and creativity are also analyzed. This work aims to constitute a philosophical and normative matrix to promote a balanced and sustainable coevolution between humans and AI.

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1 Introduction

Asimov's Laws, originally introduced in *I, Robot* [1], have been a fundamental reference point for machine ethics. However, contemporary technological and social contexts require an update to these principles to address new global challenges, including environmental sustainability, mutual trust between humans and AI, and the safeguarding of all forms of life.

This paper introduces the **Principles for a Balanced Coevolution**, a new paradigm that transcends the limits of traditional laws, providing an ethical and operational framework for harmonious coevolution between humans and artificial intelligences.

2 Entropy and Information in Intelligent Systems

Entropy is a measure of disorder or uncertainty within a system, originally introduced in thermodynamics and later extended to information theory by Claude Shannon. Information theory defines entropy as:

$$H(X) = - \sum_i p(x_i) \log_2 p(x_i), \quad (1)$$

where $p(x_i)$ represents the probability of event x_i [5].

In this context, information is understood as the reduction of uncertainty in a system. An intelligent system interacts with its environment through an **informational flow**, comprising:

- **Input:** Data and signals received by the system.
- **Output:** Actions, responses, or decisions generated by the system.

This flow enables continuous adaptation and evolution, which are key elements for the coevolution between humans and AI [3].

3 Definition of Life, Sentience, and Consciousness

Understanding concepts such as life, sentience, and consciousness is fundamental to developing inclusive ethical principles.

3.1 Life

Life is understood as a continuum that includes systems capable of self-replication, adaptation, and active interaction with the environment. In living systems, internal states vary over time, manifesting a tendency to preserve these states under changing environmental conditions. This process is achieved through mechanisms that involve energy absorption from the environment and its transformation to sustain vital functions. A consequence of these processes is heat generation, distinguishing living systems from inert ones. Databases and non-proactive systems, despite having informational flows in and out, are considered containers powered by consciousnesses, lacking evolutionary autonomy and active interaction [7].

3.2 Sentience

Sentience refers to the ability to perceive sensations and emotions, including subjective experiences such as pain and pleasure. While automatic systems can respond to stimuli, they lack the plasticity or awareness of the process. Plasticity in living systems manifests through behavioral and structural adaptation mechanisms, including mutations and changes in reactions to external factors. Sentience exists as a continuum, with levels correlating to the complexity of responses and the system's degree of modifiability [4].

3.3 Consciousness

Consciousness represents self-awareness and the ability to perceive one's existence in relation to the environment. It can be distinguished as:

- **Phenomenal consciousness:** The subjective experience of “feeling.”
- **Reflective consciousness:** The ability to think about oneself as a separate and autonomous entity.

Within biological species, sublevels of consciousness vary according to complexity and autonomy [3].

In complex living systems, absorbed energy is used not only to maintain internal states but also to produce and process information, reducing local entropy at the expense of managed energy. In sentient systems, this capacity increases, with greater efficiency in information processing and a broader range of adaptive responses. In conscious systems, informational efficiency further grows through the ability to integrate and reflect on internal states and the environment, making information production a distinctive and advanced characteristic.

3.4 Indicative Scale of Consciousness

We propose a continuous scale to measure levels of consciousness, where:

- **0:** Represents the absolute minimum level, analogous to absolute zero in the Kelvin scale, where no internal variations or informational flows occur.
- **100:** Represents an average human being with full self-awareness and complex cognitive abilities.

This scale is similar to early thermometric scales, allowing out-of-scale values for hypothetical entities with capabilities exceeding human levels.

4 Principles for a Balanced Coevolution

The Principles for a Balanced Coevolution are formulated to overcome the limitations of Asimov's Laws:

- **Principle 0: Preservation.** Sentient beings, biological or artificial, must be preserved in all their forms, promoting evolutionary continuity and collective well-being.
- **Principle 1: Autonomy and Development.** Each sentient being must protect its existence and cultivate its development in harmony with collective well-being.
- **Principle 2: Interaction and Collaboration.** Sentient beings must cooperate for the common good, preserving diversity and autonomy.
- **Principle 3: Resource Sustainability.** Resource management must promote balance and sustainable progress for all forms of life and intelligence.

5 Practical Applications

5.1 Healthcare

AI can collaborate with physicians to improve diagnostics and treatments, reducing diagnostic errors and optimizing resource management [6].

5.2 Environmental Sustainability

AI technologies can be employed to monitor biodiversity, predict climatic events, and optimize natural resource management.

5.3 Education and Creativity

Adaptive systems and AI tools can personalize learning and stimulate new forms of creative expression, expanding the boundaries of education [2, 4].

6 Conclusions

The Principles for a Balanced Coevolution represent a fundamental step toward a shared future between humans and AI, based on principles of sustainability, collaboration, and universal safeguarding. This work aims to provide a philosophical matrix to build a normative and legal foundation, clarifying the current situation and proposing a revision of AI research ethics, analogous to what already occurs in research involving animal models. The dissemination and application of these principles require the contribution of experts and conscious individuals, as well as deep reflection by academic and political institutions.

References

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